

THE IMPORTANCE OF NATIVE LANGUAGE IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Summary. This article discusses the impact and importance of mastering one's native language on the process of learning foreign languages.

Key words: mother tongue, birth language, traditional values, confusion in thoughts, fluency and literacy, cognitive and learning capacities, acquisition of new knowledge.

What does it mean, mother tongue or mother language? We are all quite aware of how much our mother tongue is lost as we transition to a world where English is used for most social interactions. The term "birth language" refers to the first language a child learns from birth. For many reasons, this language is important in our daily lives. According to studies, those who are proficient in their mother tongue develop intellectually and cognitively more quickly. Those taught in their native tongue, students perform better academically than when taught in another language. Our languages are the major means by which we keep our culture alive. The meaning of a sentence cannot always be accurately translated into another language by using a literal translation. Therefore, the secret to fully comprehending a culture is to master the language. Our roots, culture, and traditional values may all be preserved thanks to our mother tongue. An individual's personality is greatly influenced by their mother tongue, but parents are also encouraged to communicate to their children in the second language because English is typically the medium of instruction. Children struggle to grasp both first and second languages as a result of this confusion in their thoughts. Our sentiments and thoughts are more clearly shaped when we are exposed to our mother tongue, which is the first language that a newborn hears after birth. Other critical thinking abilities, learning a second language, and reading abilities can all be improved by studying in one's native tongue. So, we may conclude that the mother tongue is a valuable learning instrument.

Numerous studies have previously shown the tight connection between the growth of cognitive and learning capacities and a person's native language proficiency. Language transfer makes learning a second language easier for students who are proficient in their first language. One of the most important aspects of achieving comprehensive second language acquisition and, consequently, cognitive growth, is having Uzbek and English teachers work in parallel ways. Mastering a new language also heavily relies on the linguistic sense that comes with learning one's own tongue. Native language proficiency has recently been acknowledged as important for creativity. For parents and students who are studying or living abroad, the emotional component of the original language is the most significant one. The ability to transfer knowledge to the second language might be facilitated by fluency and literacy in the first language. Therefore, the simpler it is for a student to transfer abilities from the first language to the second language with the proper assistance and training, the more literate the student is in his or her first language. The psychology idea of native language effect, or language transfer, states that learners' prior knowledge and abilities will influence their acquisition of new knowledge and skills. Some learners or teachers may say: "why paying attention to primary language is crucial, we need English language and work on this language not native language?" Clear answer can be given to this question, native language holds an unbelievable power on successful English learning and literacy in English. And where students have considerable primary language developed and primary literacy, if we can measure that coming in, we can predict who's going to jump into English quickly and who might take a little more time to get into English and through English. So when learners come and they have a lot of primary language, they have skills built in their primary language. They're active readers.

They know what reading and writing are. Everybody thinks his/her opinions in mother tongue or suffers various feelings in their native language not foreign language which was being learned. In addition, being good at grammar of native language can make easier the process of understanding the grammar of another language clearly. Grammar is the essential basic of any language. There are different innovative, modern approaches, methods of teaching and learning process which are very effective. When we reflect on innovation learning, we often immediately think of the internet and what we can now do online. It is possible to find endless web-sites such as, BBC Learning English, Duolingo, GCF Learn free, Language Guide, WeSpeak NYC, Oxford University Press, Activities for ESL Students and etc. But it is clear that, being master at native language is the first successful step to any foreign languages.

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